

SCHOOL GUIDANCE SERVICES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: PERCEPTIONS FROM SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EDO STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated Teachers' Perception of the Influence of Guidance Services on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Edo State, Nigeria. Three research questions, three objectives and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested. The population of the study was 5,267 with a sample size of 193. The instrument titled; questionnaire on teachers' perception of the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students was used for this study to collect the data. The instrument was validated by the researcher's supervisor for face, content and construct validity. The instrument was further pilot tested using test re-test on 20 senior secondary school teachers using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient, a reliability index of 0.75 was obtained. The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis based on the research questions and null hypotheses. The hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics. The findings from the study revealed that guidance services have a great impact on senior secondary school students' academic achievement as it helps give students emotional balance while facing their studies, give proper direction in their academic and it also helps place them to benefit from vocational and educational opportunities. It concluded that guidance services help students make realistic choices and decisions about their educational plan and it also helps to build a better teacher-student relationship. The study recommended that government should as a matter of urgency establish guidance and counselling centres in all public secondary schools in Edo State; government and school management should organize seminars and conferences for teachers in the state on the importance of guidance and counselling programme irrespective of location; where government does not introduce Guidance Counsellors, Individual school should make arrangement to hire Guidance Counsellors

Keywords: *Teacher, Perception, Guidance and Counselling, Edo State, Nigeria*

Introduction

As individuals develop through the stages of life and educational attainment, they encounter problems, challenges and conflict situations. There is need, therefore, for these individuals to develop value systems, make decisions, set goals and work towards them. All these cannot be achieved without self-understanding and decision-making skills. The need to address these challenges and to promote educational success and healthy life, call for exposure to guidance services by individuals/students. Guidance is assistance or help rendered by an experienced person to a less experienced person to solve certain problems, either educationally, vocationally or personally. It is a service designed to help an individual or group of individuals in making necessary adjustment to environment whether it is within the school or outside it (Egbule, 2018). Guidance is a process of helping individuals through their own efforts to discover and develop their potentialities both for personal happiness and social usefulness. Guidance helps in

understanding one's strength and weakness. It helps an individual to develop ability to solve problems and take decisions (Yusuf, 2018). Guidance is an umbrella term embracing counselling services, appraisal services, orientation services, placement services, information services, referral services and follow-up services. All of which help an individual to know his self-understanding and consequently in making wise decisions for better adjustment (Egbo, 2015). Guidance as an organized effort of a school is to help the child develop his maximum potential. Guidance is needed for self-understanding and selfdirection; optimum development of individual; solving different problem of the individual; academic growth and development; vocational maturity, vocational choices and vocational adjustments; social personal adjustment; family life; good citizenship; for conservation and proper utilization of human resources and for national development (Egbule, 2018). Guidance is helpful not only for students and teachers in an educational institution but also to the parents, administrators, planners and community members and so on. The focus of guidance services in school is to address the needs and concerns of students at different levels of academic or educational development. Braddock (2011) stated that the purpose of guidance services in schools is to improve academic achievement, foster positive study attitudes and habit, increase acquisitions and application of conflict resolution skills and decrease school dropouts. The primary mission of a school guidance programme is to provide a broad spectrum of personnel services to the students. Denga (2011) referred to these services as cluster of formalised educational services designed by the school to assist students achieve self-knowledge or selfunderstanding which is necessary for them to attain the fullest self-development and selfrealization of their potential. Guidance services are specialized services carried out by trained guidance counsellors in addressing or meeting specific needs of students as started by (Egenti, 2020). Guidance services in school is the main field of trained school counsellors and anything that has to do with this service must be performed by guidance counsellors. School guidance counsellors are expected to devote a great deal of his/her time to counselling. The same way a teacher is employed to guide and stimulate students' learning, also is a school counsellor is employed to use his/her skills to assist students, to resolve their problems or conflicts which may be obstructing their search for knowledge. In other to solve some of these challenges, some professional services have been introduced under the school guidance programme to assist students overcome the challenges they experience at home and at school. These guidance services include orientation service which is rendered to students who often encounter difficulties in adjusting to new environment, programme or system; appraisal service which involves the use of psychometric instruments to gather data on individuals to enable both the counsellor and counsellee understand the problem. Appraisal service is the process of collecting, gathering, organizing, evaluating and interpreting information or data about the characteristics of the individual; counselling service is a personalize dialogue or interview between the counsellor and counsellee or client during which the client seeks expert's assistance from the counsellor regarding the resolution of his/her problem (Salgong, Ngumi & Chege, 2016). Placement service is the process of helping an individual to enter and make adjustment in the next stage of life development; follow-up/evaluation service is designed to assess the extent to which the guidance programme is meeting the need for which it was established. This service is mainly concerned

with the evaluation of the success, failure and problems of the guidance programme which may prompt adjustment or improvement if needs and results are identified; information service is aimed at gathering important information concerning educational, vocational and personal-social opportunities while referral service is the act of referring a case or client to the appropriate agencies or individuals for specialist attention. The counsellor must refer issues that are beyond his competence to the appropriate quarters with the consent of the client (Salgong, Ngumi & Chege, 2016). As laudable as the guidance services are in the school system, several school personnel like teachers misinterpret the good intention of the services. In consonance with this assertion, Moinid and Nyandema (2018) explained that some teachers hold a misconception about the role and function of counsellors concerning the service they render. Counsellors are sometimes view as administrative assistant that has little time to counsel students, fueling the issue is the fact that some teachers distrust counsellors, due to their apparent alignment with the administration. These teachers are cautious of counsellors observing students in their classes. They worry that their teaching methods are being evaluated as if counsellors work as the eyes and ears of the administration. Teachers who misinterpret the counsellor exhibit uncooperative and unsupportive attitude by criticizing the guidance services. These teachers believe that counsellors have little or no impact on students' behaviour or performance. They hate seeing their students working with counsellors. They find it difficult to refer students with learning difficulties to the counsellor. The refusal stems from the belief that counsellors do not help students, and sending students to the guidance and counselling office during classes is a waste of time. Teachers' perception is the thought, opinion and belief which teachers have about guidance services. Perception of teachers is very important in making guidance services a success in schools. This is to be considered when coming up with guidance and counselling programme in schools. Clark and Amatea (2004) explained that teachers are very instrumental in shaping the attitudes of students and making them do the right things. Academic achievement has been one of the most important goals of educational process. It is seen as the measure of the learner's level of knowledge, skills or performance. Academic achievement is commonly measured by examination; test or assessment. Academic achievement is the outcome of education, the extent to which a student has achieved his/her educational goals (Bossaert, Doumen, Buyse & Verschueren, 2011). Students need to possess ability to understand and manage their own behaviour and reactions which in turn allows them to have better control of their emotional, cognitive, and behavioural processes. Environmental aggravation such as lack or inadequate maternal or paternal care, emotional, physical and sexual abuse, and the experience of loss early in life are major risk factors that can affect a student's wellbeing (Adikwu, Oguiche, Usman & Olabode, 2023). It is based on above notion that the researchers set out to embark on this study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to find out Teachers' Perception of the Influence of Guidance Services on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Edo State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Find out teachers' perception of the influence of guidance service on academic achievement senior secondary school students in Edo State.
- ii. Examine teachers' perception of the influence of guidance service on academic achievement senior secondary school students in Edo State based on gender.
- iii. Examine teachers' perception of the influence of guidance service on academic achievement senior secondary school students in Edo State based location.

Research Questions

1. What is the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State?
2. What is the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State based on gender?
3. What is the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students Edo State based on location?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses has been formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between rural and urban teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State.

Conceptual Framework

Guidance Services

Guidance services prepare students to assume increasing responsibility for their decision and grow in their ability to understand and accept the result of their choices (Gibson, 2010). The ability to make such intelligent choices is not innate, but like other abilities, must be developed. The purpose of guidance services in schools according to (Erford, 2011) is to improve academic performance, foster positive study attitudes and habit, increase acquisitions and application of conflict resolution skills and decrease school dropouts. The primary mission of a school's guidance programme is to provide a broad spectrum of personnel services to the students. Denga (2011) referred to the guidance services as cluster of formalised educational services designed by the school to assist students to achieve self-knowledge or self-understanding which is necessary for them to attain the fullest self-development and self-realization of their potential. These services include: appraisal service, information service, counselling service, placement service, orientation service, referral service, follow-up/evaluation service. Appraisal service involves the use of tests and non-test instruments to collect, analyse and interpret data of students to understand themselves better. It also affords counsellors the opportunity of having insight into the strengths and weaknesses of students. Information service is tailored towards equipping students with the necessary information in the areas of educational, vocational and personal social. Counselling service is a face to face interaction between the counsellor and the students, through which students are assisted

towards overcoming obstacles to their academic, vocational, personal social progress and other life needs. Placement service is concerned with assisting students to adjust to the next stage of development whether in school or on the job. Orientation service is designed to familiarize fresh students with their environment. It is a process of initiating an individual to a work or learning situation and of instructing him about rules, regulations and responsibilities, as an introduction to a new situation. Referral service affords the school counsellor an opportunity to refer a case to specialists. Follow-up/evaluation service is designed to ascertain the extent to which the guidance programme previously carried out by the school is meeting the objectives for which it was established and also to monitor the progress of students in their work places (Ardo, 2017). Guidance services are, therefore, necessary in secondary schools where adolescent stage is at its peak. At this stage, students need to clarify their goals and values, strengthen their interests and aspirations. Some major needs for guidance services in schools are changes in educational system; students' potentialities and limitations; choice of subjects and careers; gainful employment; school dropout (or educational wastage); falling standard of education and students' indiscipline/moral decadence. Usman (2020) listed some importance of guidance and counselling services in schools as:

1. **Population Mobility:** there is an observable steady movement of people from one part of the country to the other. As far as migration is going on and will continue for a long time to come, therefore there is need for guidance and counseling services in schools.
2. **Emotional Illness:** lack of data has made it impossible to make any authoritative statement on childhood psychiatric disorders in Nigeria. It is possible, however, that some children may be afflicted and whatever the proportion is, they deserve attention through guidance and counselling services.
3. **Broken Homes:** phenomenon of broken homes is much with us and on the increase too. Children from broken homes often have problems of a social or emotional nature that are more serious than the problems of those who suffer from lack of supervision and companionship. Therefore, an organized guidance and counselling services is needed to assist them.
4. **Physical and Health Problems:** it is a common sight in our schools to see physically handicapped students in the same class with others. There is also the presence of malnourished students and sick children whose problems go undetected. Children suffering from malnutrition shows signs of weakness or sleepiness in class. Sadly enough, majority of the class teachers are in no position to address their problems. Therefore, there is need for guidance services.
5. **Adolescents in Schools:** in most schools in Nigeria, there is the presence of adolescents, particularly in rural areas. The problems, needs and concerns of these students will definitely be different from those of the younger children often found by side with them in the same class. Guidance services are needed to assist these groups of students in the classroom.
6. **Social Ills:** among the social ills that are prevalent in the society include; lack of respect for elders by the younger generation. Although Nigeria is heading towards development, our values, norms such as respect for others should not go with development. These values may be restored if guidance and counselling become operational right from early stages of a child's development.

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement can be seen as the knowledge gained or achieved which is assessed by marks by a teacher. The parameter for employment, work placement, and human advancement both in public and private organization depend strongly on academic achievement. Also, due consideration is given to grades of results when giving admission to schools all over the world. For this reason, it put those concerned under serious pressure in the process, since work placement and in life in general is absolutely the product of success in examination or academic achievement (Adikwu, Oguche, Usman and Olabode, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

The Rational Emotive Theory by Albert Ellis emphasizes that humans do not get emotionally disturbed by unfortunate circumstances, but by how they construct their views of these circumstances through their languages, evaluative beliefs, meanings and philosophies about the world, themselves and others. Ellis came to regard irrational beliefs and illogical thinking as the major cause of most emotional disturbances. In his view, negative events do not by themselves cause depression or anxiety, rather emotional disorder result when a person perceives the events in an irrational way. It is based on the premise that whenever we become upset, it is not the events taking place in our lives that upset us; but the beliefs that we hold that cause us to become depressed, anxious, enraged, etc. Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy (REBT) can be significant to this study because it is a therapy applied in an educational process in which the therapist often teaches the client how to identify rational and self-defeating beliefs and philosophies which in nature are extreme, unrealistic, illogical and absolutist and then to forcefully and actively dispute them and replace them with more rational and self-helping beliefs. One of the main goals of REBT is to show the client that whenever unpleasant and unfortunate activating events occur in people's lives, they have a choice of making themselves feel healthily and self-helping or making themselves feel unhealthily and self-defeating, horrified, terrified, panicking, depressed, self-hating and self-pitying. By attaining and ingraining a more rational and self-constructive philosophy of themselves, others and the world, people often are more likely to behave in more life-serving and adaptive ways. Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy can be very effective in guidance and counselling services such as; counselling service, referral service, appraisal services and followup/evaluation services.

Methodology

The design adopted for this study is descriptive survey research design. This is a research method that describes a given state of affairs at a particular time (Afu, Oguche, Usman and Gimba, 2023). This research design permits the gathering of information through the use of questionnaire from a population based on appropriate sampling techniques. Also, descriptive survey research was considered suitable since it would solicit for information or responses from the respondents on the problem under investigation. It was on this basis that the researcher decided to use descriptive survey design. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire titled: Teachers' Perception of the Influence of Guidance Services on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students (TPIGSAASSS). The TPIGSAASSS was a 30 item instrument designed among a modified fourpoint Likert scale. The questionnaire was validated (face, content and construct

validity) by a team of experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Abuja. During this process, items that considered to be vague, ambiguous or irrelevant were removed to ensure that the questionnaire serve the purpose for which it was designed. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted. Using the test-retest method of reliability, the two set of scores obtained from the pilot test were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). The reliability index value of 0.75 was obtained. To collect the data required for the study, a letter of introduction from obtained from the Head of Department to the principals of the selected schools. The letter explained the purpose of the study and sought consent of the participants. The statistical tools that were used in analyzing the collected data include mean, t-test and Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient statistical technique at 0.05 level of significance. To answer the research questions, the study adopted a decision rule based on midpoint of 2.50, this is because the instrument was created on a 4-point scale. The hypotheses were tested using t-test in order to compare the relationship between variables and determine difference between two variables (male and female responses).

Results

Research question one: What is the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State?

Table 1: Perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State

N = 193

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	Guidance services improve Students’ learning	106	40	28	19	3.21	1.02	Agreed
2.	Teachers see the school	51	72	41	23	2.35	0.98	Disagreed
3.	Teachers view counsellors’ orientation role as unnecessary	97	48	19	29	3.10	1.09	Agreed in school system
4.	Guidance is given to students On future career not for	59	86	23	25	2.93	0.97	Agreed academic purpose
5.	Guidance services in school is	73	30	22	22	2.97	0.98	Agreed a distraction to class activities
6.	Information about educational Requirements are always given	53	62	47	31	2.71	1.04	Agreed to students
7.	Guidance services help to	95	43	13	13	2.86	0.83	Agreed place students into the right Classes based on skills and intelligence
8.	Guidance services helps teachers adopt better teaching techniques							

- 23 31 86 53 2.12 0.95 Disagreed
9. Guidance services does not make students adjust fast to the 18 77 51 47 2.34 0.95 Disagreed school
10. Teachers' attitude towards school counsellor is a threat to 7 28 65 93 1.74 0.84
Disagreed the counselling unit
11. Guidance services help to give
Students proper direction in 45 64 67 17 2.71 0.92 Agreed their academics
12. It helps students realize areas
Where they need improvement 69 43 81 0 2.94 0.88 Agreed academically
13. Guidance services helps teachers to understand the 39 4 63 87 1.97 1.13 Disagreed weaknesses of
their students
14. Guidance services helps to give students emotional
56 70 28 39 2.74 1.08 Agreed balance while facing their studies
15. Students living their class for
Counselling activities can be 47 59 52 35 2.61 1.04 Agreed affected academically
16. Students are well placed for them to benefit from
21 83 77 12 2.59 0.76 Agreed vocational and educational opportunities
17. Counselling helps students
Improve in their academic 93 47 7 46 2.97 1.21 Agreed studies
18. Guidance services help students compose themselves
Appropriately in the face of 74 56 49 14 2.98 0.96 Agreed challenges and
adverse
Conditions
19. Students use counselling as an excuse for not attending
Classes
48 63 53 29 2.67 1.01 Agreed
20. Guidance service can bring about positive change
in the mindset of students
65 93 28 7 3.12 0.78 Agreed
21. Guidance services help students through their 31 88 17 57 2.48 1.08 Disagreed psychosocial
development
22. It helps students make realistic
Choices and decisions about 98 72 22 1 3.38 0.70 Agreed their educational plans
Guidance services in school helps to create good personal-
52 85 41 15 2.90 0.88 Agreed social opportunities for
Students
23. Guidance services makes teachers plan well for their 33 38 69 53 2.26
1.04 Disagreed teaching period

24.	Guidance services in school help students to develop high								
67	49 53 24	2.82	1.04	Agreed aspirations	towards				their academic pursuits
25.	School counsellor should be								
46	70 77 0	2.84	0.78	Agreed given some subject	to teach				
26.	Guidance services in school help in the total development	107	63	14	9	3.39	0.81		
	Agreed of the student								
27.	Guidance services helps to build a better teacher-student	41	46	84	22	2.55	0.95	Agreed	relationship
28.	Guidance services will help to								
	Minimize school dropout	123	59	0	11	3.52	0.77	Agreed among students	
29.	Drug abuse and cultism among students can be control with								
48	97 33 15	2.92	0.85	Agreed functioning guidance services	in schools				
	Sectional Mean	2.76	1.04	Agreed					

The analysis in the above table shows agreement in most items which are teachers' perception of the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State except items 2, 8, 9, 10, 13, 21 and 24 which are relating to teachers' disposition towards guidance services. This revealed that guidance services has influence on academic achievement (sectional mean = 2.76, which is greater than the critical value of 2.50). Research Question Two: What is the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students' in Edo State based on gender? Table 2: Mean Score on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement senior secondary school students in Edo State based on gender

N = 193 Gender	No	Mean	Std. Dev
Male	85	2.79	1.02
Female	108	2.74	1.05

Result on Table 2 shows the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State based on gender. Male respondents indicated mean score of 2.79, while female respondents indicated a mean score of 2.74. The mean score on influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State were higher for the male teachers than their female counterpart even though both have a mean score that is higher than the critical value of 2.50. The implication of this result is that the male senior secondary school teachers in Edo State perceived that guidance services have influence on academic achievement of secondary school students. Research Question Three: What is the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State based on location? Table 3: Mean Score on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior

N = 193 Location	No	Mean	Std. Dev
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Urban	128	2.72	1.06
Rural	65	2.83	1.01

Result on Table 3 shows the perception of teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State based on location. The urban respondents indicated a mean score of 2.72, while rural respondents indicated a mean score of 2.83. The mean score on influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State were higher for the rural teachers than their urban counterpart even though both have a mean score that is higher than the critical value of 2.50. The implication of this result is that the rural senior secondary school teachers in Edo State perceived that guidance services have influence on academic achievement of secondary school students.

Test of Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State. Table 4: Two-tailed t-test result in respect of male and female teachers on the influence of guidance

Services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State

N = 193	<u>N</u>	<u>X</u>	<u>S.D</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>t-</u>	<u>Std.</u>	<u>Sig@0.05</u>	<u>Decision</u>
<u>Gender</u>					<u>value</u>	<u>Error</u>		
Male	85	2.79	1.02					
193	0.315	0.151	0.753	Not significant				
Female	108	2.74	1.05					

Result on Table 4 showed that there was no significant difference between male and female teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State (p= 0.753, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance). As a result, the hypothesis was accepted. In other words, the opinion of male and female teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement are not obviously different.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between rural and urban teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State. Table 5: Two-tailed t-test result in respect of rural and urban teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic

<u>Location</u>	<u>N</u>	<u>X</u>	<u>S.D</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>t-Value</u>	<u>Std. Error</u>	<u>Sig@0.05</u>	<u>Decision</u>
Urban	128	2.72	1.06					
achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State.								
Rural	65	2.83	1.01					

N = 193 193 0.315 0.159 0.481 Not significant

Result on Table 5 showed that there was no significant difference in the responses of urban and rural teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State (p= 0.481, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance). As a result, the hypothesis

was accepted. In other words, the opinion of urban and rural teachers on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement are not obviously different.

Discussion of Findings

Findings showed that guidance services have a great influence on academic achievement of senior secondary school students as it helps give students emotional balance while facing their studies, give proper direction in their academic and it also help place them to benefit from vocational and educational opportunities. In support of this finding, Tambuwal (2014) stated that guidance services is an integral part of the school system and those who consult the school counsellor often are better adjusted academically. He also affirmed that such students find their way around complicated curriculum and this in turn enhances their academic performance.

The study also found no significant differences between male and female teachers on the perceived influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State. According to Eremie and BOB-Manuel (2020), teachers irrespective of their gender has a positive perception about orientation services, counselling services, information services and appraisal services in schools. Dickson (2012) stated that guidance and counselling services were offered in schools and 82.4% of the principals considered it important. The study found that urban and rural teachers did not differ significantly in their view on the influence of guidance services on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State. Egbule (2018) in her study perception of teachers on the guidance and counselling needs of secondary school students stated that teachers perceive guidance and counselling needs of secondary school students in a positive view irrespective of location.

Conclusion

The study concludes that guidance services have a great influence on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Edo State. The respondents (teachers) agreed that guidance services help students realize the area where they need improvement, it helps give students emotional balance, it helps in the total development of the student, create good personal-social opportunities, it helps students make realistic choices and decisions about their educational plan and it also helps to build a better teacher-student relationship.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study.

1. Government should as a matter of urgency establish guidance and counselling centres in all public secondary schools in Edo State.
2. Government and school management should organize seminars and conferences for teachers in the state on the importance of guidance and counselling programme irrespective of location.
3. Where Government does not introduce Guidance Counsellors, individual school should make arrangement to hire Guidance Counsellors

4. This calls for Guidance Counsellors to form counselling consultancy firms where universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, monotechnic and secondary schools can hire them on ad hoc basis to render guidance seminars for their students.

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